

IDENTITY, LANGUAGE LEARNING, AND CRITICAL PEDAGOGIES IN DIGITAL TIMES

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Abstract. *This paper explores the ways in which critical pedagogies have adapted to the evolving power dynamics and connections in our increasingly digital society. The creation and performance of identities, power structures and relationships, and social and educational disparities are all examined as important advances in identity studies that relate to the digital. Moreover, it focuses on two major challenges associated with the shift to digital media in language learning.*

Keywords: *digital media, educational inequities, technological advancements, cultural identity, cognitive development and socializing.*

Аннотация. *В этой статье исследуются способы, с помощью которых критическая педагогика адаптировалась к развивающейся динамике власти и связям в нашем все более цифровом обществе. Создание и функционирование идентичностей, властных структур и отношений, а также социальных и образовательных различий рассматриваются как важные достижения в исследованиях идентичности, связанных с цифровыми технологиями. Более того, основное внимание уделяется двум основным проблемам, связанным с переходом на цифровые медиа в изучении языка.*

Ключевые слова: *цифровые медиа, неравенство в образовании, технологические достижения, культурная идентичность, когнитивное развитие и общение.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada tanqidiy pedagogikaning tobora ko'payib borayotgan raqamli jamiyatimizdagi rivojlanayotgan kuch dinamikasi va aloqalariga moslashish usullari o'rganiladi. Shaxsiyatlar, kuch tuzilmalari va munosabatlari, ijtimoiy va ta'limiy tafovutlarning yaratilishi va ishlashi raqamli bilan bog'liq bo'lgan shaxsni o'rganishda muhim yutuqlar sifatida ko'rib chiqiladi. Bundan tashqari, u til o'rganishda raqamli mediaga o'tish bilan bog'liq ikkita asosiy muammoga qaratilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *raqamli media, ta'limdagi tengsizliklar, texnologik yutuqlar, madaniy o'ziga xoslik, kognitiv rivojlanish va ijtimoiylashuv.*

Introduction. The practices of classrooms and communities also grow more complex as learners manage their investments in language and literacy while they enact a variety of dynamic identities in this new world order. In order to comprehend how identity has changed into a crucial concept in language learning, this research looks at the early conceptualizations of identity and the prior studies that impacted them. Then, as significant developments in identity studies that connect with the digital, the production and performance of identities, structures and relations of power, and social and educational inequities are studied. Besides that, it focuses on two significant difficulties in language acquisition related to the digital transition. First, the variety of venues that learners can interact with necessitates the mastery of fresh, ever-evolving literacies. In

order to recognize and traverse systemic mechanisms of control, it is now more difficult to see how the processes of power operate. It ends by suggesting specific scientific fields that will aid in developing transformational critical pedagogies: problems with political economics, digital exclusion, and technological advancements.

Scholars who were involved into second-language identification in the 1970s and 1980s tended to distinguish between social identity and cultural identity. "Social identity" was understood to refer to how a language learner's link to the greater social environment is regulated by institutions including families, schools, businesses, social services, and legal systems (Gumperz, 1982). On the other hand, "Cultural identity" referred to the connection between a person and members of a specific ethnic group (such as Mexicans and Japanese), who having a common background, a shared language, and comparable worldviews. Atkinson (1999) pointed out that earlier conceptions of cultural identification had a tendency to problematic issues and define communities. Multimedia self-presentations of students have the potential to fix identity representations and have a complicated, lasting impact on their lives, just as the digital alters perceptions of time and space by making items eternally present and permanent (Nelson et al. 2008). In parallel, ethnographers explore digital frontiers where the lines between the private and public are blurred. This poses new ethical, informed consent, and researcher identification problems. Research groups have flocked to this area to study and find new educational prospects as the digital environment created by new media is a much more commonplace environment of cognitive development and socializing.

Without any doubt, the twenty-first century requires learners to enact numerous identities and linguistic sequences whilst constantly posed in novel, frequently undetectable ways as they navigate new digital arenas ruled by diverse value systems. After reading this article I found out that one of the biggest issues facing language teaching in the digital age is how educators can map out these increasingly complicated places while juggling conflicting ideologies and pedagogies. In order to overcome this issue, researchers in language education have worked to create novel conceptions of identity that reflect the shifting dynamics between language learners and society. This study challenges educational agents to think about the physical circumstances that support language acquisition by focusing on how language learners and teachers manage power relations. Investigation on identity, language acquisition, and critical pedagogies must deal with new issues of power and access in this evolving digital environment, especially when examining how the findings might be applied in the classroom.

Findings:

Identity studies have adopted several motifs as the opportunities of the multimedia have made it possible for creative ways of self-representation and a variety of social engagement venues. While more critical study has concentrated on questions of power and social injustice, interpretive research has looked at the achievement and development of digitally mediated identities. Three recurring topics in the field of critical pedagogies will be discussed:

- a) The creation and performance of identities;
- b) Power structures and relations;

c) Social and educational injustices.

Identities will achieve sustained competitive advantage concept in the sociocultural component of language education research and a hot matter of debate among academics, educators, and researchers.

When it comes to the connections with other prior courses, It is natural that the changes that occur in the implementation of language acquisition in each period encounter a number of difficulties. Identity is a crucial concept in the study of language learning. It is described as "how a person views his or her views on society, how that relationship is formed through spatial and temporal, and how the individual defines possibilities and options." It does not specifically determine language, and language does not inevitably determine somebody's identity, but each have an impact on the other. People can choose the language they need to use to interact with other communities based on their identities according to how many languages they are able to speak. An essential component of cultural identity is language. It is how we pass on our true selves from one generation to the next. We communicate and convey our culture and its beliefs through language.

Conclusion:

Globalization has intensified in recent years due to the quick advancement of technological tools as well as the escalating conservative strains on many countries. Digital stories, a type of identity text, have emerged as a significant way for scholars to comprehend how students create identities through access. Learners are given the opportunity to express themselves creatively in a variety of media, which can lead to gently changing attitudes.

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